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plants and complete plants for each agronomic trait evaluated was computed independently in both moisture regimes (see table).

A high significant positive correlation was observed for plant height between regenerated and complete plants in both moisture regimes. In the control, such association was also seen for number of tillers and productive tillers. In the low-moisture stress treatment, grain yield from regenerated plants after stress showed a significant positive association with complete plants and a significant negative association at maturity. In the control, grain yield from regenerated plants at maturity had a significant positive association with complete plants. Plants manifested innate differences in several qualitative traits and relative differences in quantitative traits. Sufficient seeds were produced for generation advancement and grain yield.

Correlation between single-tiller regenerated plants and complete plants for four agronomic traits.

Trait	Well-watered control			Low-moisture stress		
	After stress 65 DAS	At flowering	At maturity	After stress 65 DAS	At flowering	At maturity
Plant height	0.73**	0.91**	0.93**	0.93**	0.89**	0.75**
Tiller no.	0.62*	0.70*	0.88**	0.15	0.15	0.10
Productive tillers	0.62*	0.60*	0.48*	-0.24	-0.58*	-0.26
Grain yield	0.11	0.34	0.52*	0.54*	0.22	-0.59*

** = significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively. DAS = days after sowing.

The single-tiller method could be effective in advancing generations, with or without additional crossing. The grain yield for single-tiller crops does not represent the genotype's true potential, which could be assessed by progeny testing with seeds obtained.

References

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Dhan Laxmi and Richharia, very early rice varieties released in Bihar, India

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Flood and drought periodically affect rice in Bihar. Sometimes, flood and drought occur at the same time in different parts of the state. Early maturing varieties in such situations have an advantage as a preflood crop in low-lying areas or as rainfed upland rice when rains are scanty, resulting in drought. In addition, they also have potential for planting during the boro season. Very early maturing varieties (<100 d) such as Heera, Prasana, and Sattari, re-

leased earlier at the national level, have not been adopted by farmers mainly because of low yield and susceptibility to various diseases and insect pests.

We started to develop very early rice varieties in the early 1980s. Numerous crosses were made involving very early maturing varieties as one of the parents. Turant Dhan derived from the cross Sattari/Rasi was consequently developed (Thakur et al 1995). Segregating populations

were raised in both the wet and boro (Oct-Nov and April-May) seasons for selection. The boro-season crop faces acute low temperature, even as low as 4 °C at the seedling stage, and heat at flowering. Productivity, however, is very high (Thakur et al 1994). Several very early maturing improved germplasm accessions were identified and tested in both the wet and boro seasons. RAU1344-3-2 derived from ES 1-2-3/IR36 and RAU1345-5-2 de-